

INTERFACE MODELLING IN LAMINATE COMPOSITES FOR FREE-EDGE EFFECTS ANALYSIS

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SUMMARY: Two interface models based on physical considerations are suggested and used to analyse the free-edge effects in unidirectional multi-layered composites. These models question the pertinence of the classical perfect interface model to represent the interface physical reality. The first model is transition spatial evolution behavior law defined for an interlayer according to the laying direction. It is based on a microscopic analysis of the fiber distribution in the interface vicinity between two layers. The numerical simulation of this model gives exact stress tensor in all the laminate, especially the values of the interlaminar stresses which verify exactly the free-edge conditions. The second model is an interface law defined on material surface, resulting from the resolution of a problem to the limits on the interlayer, simulating a very thin flexible layer. This model also gives no singular free-edge interlaminar stresses.

KEYWORDS: unidirectional laminates, free-edge effects, transition behavior law, wall effect, asymptotic expansion method, material surface law, singular interlaminar stresses

INTRODUCTION

The idea that the quality of a composite does not depend only on the nature and properties of its constituents but also of their binding region is now known [1]. Many samples exist where the interface modelling wake has been considered responsible for real or supposed miscalculations [2,3]. Enhancing the interfacial region analysis is not a simple task, as this zone does not exist itself, it is formed during the material manufacture [4]. Thus, some unidirectional thermodurcissable laminate processes like RTM, induce microscopic scale changes, that manifest by resin focusing at the interface. This focusing is due notably to specific fiber distribution at the interface vicinity, generated by "the wall effect", introduced by Billot for laminate composites [5], Fig. 1.

The aim of this work is to investigate the influence of a refined interfacial regional description on free edge effect and to compare this approach with classical methods of analysis.

Usually, at the free-edge vicinity of a laminate plate, a complex 3D state stresses is observed, presenting an important concentration effect, able to provoke delamination failures. The classical theories or the piece wise approach do not reveal this state of stresses, many structural free-edge effect developments have been then proposed these last years, [6]. In these models, the interlaminar interface is commonly assimilated to a perfect surface, or sometimes to a very thin layer of an adhesive material, [7]. These approaches, after simulation, generate singular free-edge interlaminar stresses. These singularities create

difficulties in the application of onset delamination criteria, as they overestimate the physical interlaminar stresses, [8].

In this work, we start by setting a transition behavior model for the interface region or the interlayer. This model constitutes the essence of our approach. The evolutive law has therefore been served in a 3D finite element tensile test simulation of a $(0^\circ, 90^\circ)_s$ laminate. Comparisons with classical results show that our approach allows the best perception of the stresses in the totality of the composite laminate, especially at the free edge.

This approach presents the inconvenient of being numerically expensive and badly adapted to the study of any multi-layer containing several interfaces. We have therefore decided to develop an interface law defined on a material surface, translating the evolutive continue behavior of the interface region to render our approach more profitable. In order to achieve this, we have used the asymptotic expansion method where the interface thickness constitutes the small parameter of the problem.

We obtain a first interface law, asymptotically equivalent, to transmission conditions through a thin interlayer, relating by stiffness the stresses interface vector to the displacement jumps. Note that, we have mathematically obtained the supposed imperfect interface model proposed in [3].

Several basic numerical tests have permitted the theoretical validation of the interface law. The interlayer was successively discretized for different values of its thickness. The numerical stiffnesses values converge when the thickness decreases towards the theoretical values given by the interface law.

Furthermore, the interface law is implemented in the industrial finite element software ABAQUS. Different tests validate the interface card implementation and show its capacity to restore the stress and the displacement vector at the interface correctly. Finally, this law has been used to analyse the free-edge effects in $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ laminate in extension, presenting a very thin flexible interface, representing an adhesive material.

INTERLAYER TRANSITION NOTION

The classical piecewise approach that averages the behavior in the thickness of each layer and assimilates the interfacial region as a perfect adherence surface is only an approximation of the reality. Indeed, the interface, which is the area separating two layers, is a layer of very weak thickness, Fig. 1.

This layer is constituted in part of resin in the case of organic matrix laminates, with a specific fiber distribution.

So, to describe more clearly the interlaminar unidirectional laminate interface, we propose a model that takes into account the three dimensional and heterogeneous nature of the interface. This model is based on the wall effect notion, a classical notion in granular mechanics [10].

Fig.1: Laminate micrographic section (S. I. Anderson and K. Nielsen, ECCM 5 1992)

Wall Effect Comments

The wall effect allows us to demonstrate the fiber specific spatial distribution in the vicinity of a contact surface. In the case of a laminate, the contact surface can be a layer whose reinforcements are oriented differently to the studied layer or the composite fabric mould wall.

Let Ω' be a longitudinal surface of a layer, parallel to the wall Ω , Fig. 2. In full mass, by unit area of this surface Ω' , the fiber section area S_f and the resin one S_r are in the same proportion as the volume rates ($S_f + S_r = V_f + V_r = 1$).

If Ω' and Ω are too close in comparison with the fiber diameter, the surface fiber fraction S_f becomes insignificant compared to the resin fraction S_r ($S_f \ll S_r$).

Fig. 2: Definition of the wall effect and the transition area

In contact with the wall, by a geometrical effect, the layer enriches in resin and sufficiently far from the wall by a distance equal to the fiber diameter Φ_f , we find the full mass composition, the fiber rate is then equal to its average value \bar{V}_f . This description explains for example the external appearance of the moulding manufactured composite.

Transition Behavior Law

Fig. 3: Fiber rate distribution along the thickness
 ($\bar{V}_f = 50\%$, $\Phi_f = 20 \mu m$)

Fig. 4: Theoretical evolution of V_f

The study of volume fraction of the resin is based on the definition of a representative volume (or slice) of a periodic fiber arrangement whose width corresponds to the periodicity.

Therefore, we quantify the volume fraction of the fibers in the region situated between the plan Ω' and the wall Ω . We show that the distribution according to x_3 depends, for a given arrangement, on the diameter and the average volume rate of the fibers in the layer.

The curve, Fig. 3, represents this distribution in the case of an hexagonal fiber arrangement. In numerical simulations, we have retained an evolutive fiber distribution in a reduced zone whose thickness is equal to the fiber diameter, Fig. 4.

The elasticity tensor of the transition region, C_{ijkl} , is then obtained by a classical homogenisation technique [9]. It appears as a function of x_3 due to the x_3 evolution fiber rate, linking up with the behaviors of the adjacent layers, Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Evolutive behavior law

NUMERICAL STUDY

The laminate studied is made of 4 elementary unidirectional layers, $(0^\circ, 90^\circ)_s$, with the same thickness, h , Fig. 6. The layers are transversely isotropic with the following characteristics :

$$E_{11} = 38250 \text{ MPa} ; E_{22} = E_{33} = 9200 \text{ MPa}$$

$$G_{23} = 3135 \text{ MPa} ; G_{13} = G_{12} = 3770 \text{ MPa} ; \nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.325$$

Fig.6 a: Laminate plate $(0^\circ, 90^\circ)_s$

Fig. 6 b: F. E. modeled part

A refined meshing of the plate has been implemented, Fig. 7, using quadratic 20 nodes solid finite elements listed C3D20 on the industrial software ABAQUS.

Fig. 7: F. E. meshing

It contains 1200 elements and 26259 degrees of freedom. This specific element permits the introduction of an evolutive law on the thickness.

Two numerical simulation types have been carried out :

- the first corresponds to the classical perfect piecewise approach of the interface, without a transition law, referenced "SLT".
- the second corresponds to the proposed model and takes into account the evolutive transition law identified previously, referenced "LTE".

Fig. 8: σ_{33} along the interface with an expansion at the vicinity of the free edge

Fig. 9: σ_{23} along the interface with an expansion at the vicinity of the free edge

The results in figures 8, 9, 10 and the expansions associated, show the concentration effect expected of the stresses at the intersection of the free edge and the interface. On the other hand, successive meshing refinements at the interface and the free edge vicinity show the non singular and singular character of the free-edge interlaminar stresses respectively, when using a continuous evolutive behavior interface law and conditions of a classical perfect interface.

So, the taking into account of the fiber specific distribution in the vicinity of the interface leads to more physical stresses [12], which are more appropriate for delamination onset criteria applications.

In addition, this approach allows us to consider a resin interlayer met in some injection manufacturing processes (RTM). Similarly, the existence of transition film at the composite periphery during their manufacturing with kit under pressure can be simulated.

These numerical calculations, undertaken in ABAQUS, have needed a very thin discretization of the interface region. Nevertheless, it is necessary to note that the cost of this approach render it badly adapted to the study of any industrial multilayer; this is why, we have decided to develop a simplified transition element, so as to integrate them in a more industrial meshing, making the approach numerically profitable.

Thus, a first interface model based on asymptotic calculations is established. It permits us to substitute this interlayer discretization for an interfacial law defined on a material surface without thickness. Its numerical implementation in an industrial software code resulted to a representative interface card of a transition layer composed by an adhesive material.

Fig. 10: σ_{33} along the free edge ($x_2=0$)

ASYMPTOTIC INTERFACE LAWS

Using asymptotic development, we seek to replace the very thin interlayer behavior law given in Fig. 5. To make matters simpler, we assume, that it concerns a linear elastic behavior per part that connects with the adjacent layers behavior :

$$C_{ijkl}^e(x_3) = \begin{cases} C_{ijkl}^r + \frac{2x_3}{el} (C_{ijkl}^+ - C_{ijkl}^r) & 0 \leq x_3 \leq +\frac{el}{2} \\ C_{ijkl}^r - \frac{2x_3}{el} (C_{ijkl}^- - C_{ijkl}^r) & -\frac{el}{2} \leq x_3 \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

C_{ijkl}^r represents the elasticity tensor of the resin. e is a dimensionless number less than 1. l is a length equal thereafter to l , which will not affect the general character of the statement. More flexible than the adjacent layers, the interfacial region behavior and particularly the resin one is a function of its dimensionless thickness :

$$C_{ijkl}^r = e \tilde{C}_{ijkl}^r \quad (2)$$

\tilde{C}_{ijkl}^r being a finite entity of the same order as C_{ijkl}^+ and C_{ijkl}^- .

So, the tensor $C_{ijkl}^e(x_3)$ becomes for example :

$$C_{ijkl}(y_3) = e \left(1 - \frac{2y_3}{l} \right) \tilde{C}_{ijkl}^r + \frac{2y_3}{l} C_{ijkl}^+ \quad 0 \leq y_3 = \frac{x_3}{e} \leq \frac{l}{2} \quad (3)$$

and appears as the sum of three different behavior representative terms :

$$C_{ijkl}(y_3) = \tilde{C}_{ijkl}(y_3) e^m \quad (4)$$

where m successively takes the values $m=1$, $m=0$.

The typical studied tensor is then an orthotropic rigidity tensor, function of the expanded variable $y_3 = x_3 / e$, the reduced thickness e and a real power value m .

We use the asymptotic expansion that consists to research displacements and stresses in the interlayer function of the small parameter e under the form :

$$\begin{aligned} {}^e U(x_1, x_2, x_3) &= U^0(x_1, x_2, y_3) + e U^1(x_1, x_2, y_3) + \alpha(e^2) \\ {}^e \sigma(x_1, x_2, x_3) &= e^{n_0} \sigma^{n_0}(x_1, x_2, y_3) + e^{n_0+1} \sigma^{n_0+1}(x_1, x_2, y_3) + \alpha(e^{n_0+2}) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

n_0 depending on m value.

Displacement and stresses $({}^e U, {}^e \sigma)$ are solutions of a classical problem with perfect adhesion conditions on the interfaces I+ et I- between the interlayer and the adjacent layers. To this problem, we add a "non-interpenetrability" physical condition :

$${}^e U(x_3 - \xi e) - {}^e U(x_3) = 0 \quad -\frac{e}{2l} \leq x_3 \leq 0 \quad 0 \leq \xi \leq 1 \quad (6)$$

By replacing (4) in these equations, we obtain succession balance equations corresponding to the development orders. At the first order, the resolution of the problem provides the following interface law asymptotically equivalent to transmission conditions through a very thin layer, whose behavior is given by (3).

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \text{if } m \geq 1 & \begin{aligned} [\sigma_{i3}^0] &= 0 \\ \sigma_{i3}^0 &= k_i [U_i^0] \quad k_i = \frac{1}{\langle \frac{1}{\tilde{C}_{i3i3}} \rangle} \end{aligned} \\ \text{if } m < 1 & \begin{aligned} [\sigma_{i3}^0] &= 0 \\ [U_i^0] &= 0 \end{aligned} \end{array} \right. \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma_{33}^0 < 0 \Rightarrow [U_3^0] = 0 \quad (8)$$

In these relations i is not an added sign, the symbols $\langle \rangle$ and $[]$ respectively designate the thickness averaging $\langle f \rangle = \int_{-1/2}^{+1/2} f dy_3$ and the jump

$$[f] = f\left(y_3 = +\frac{1}{2}\right) - f\left(y_3 = -\frac{1}{2}\right) = f^+ - f^- \text{ operators.}$$

Mechanical interpretation of the interface law :

When $m < 1$, a case corresponding either to quite flexible or rigid layer, we find perfect transmission conditions.

When $m < 1$, a case corresponding to a flexible or a very flexible layer, we obtain interface conditions that permit sliding and decohesion, the stiffnesses (k_1, k_2, k_3) being respectively the coefficients of elastic sliding and decohesion.

- when these coefficients take infinite values, we find again the transmission law of perfect interface, $m < 1$.
- when they take zero values, the interface does not ensure its binding function (stresses transmission at the interface, $\sigma^0 = 0, m > 1$).
- when k_1, k_2 and k_3 take intermediate values, the interface is elastic.
- when the normal stress σ_{33} is negative (crushing), the relation (8) imposes the normal displacement continuity, according to the laying direction.

The interface region plays a role in the global composite system resistance through stiffnesses k_1, k_2 and k_3 , which control the transfer level of stresses.

NUMERICAL LAW INTERFACE TREATMENT

In this paragraph, we are going to show that previously established interface conditions can be implemented in an industrial software ABAQUS.

- Elementary tests are first undertaken to validate both the interface law on the theoretical aspect and its implementation.
- The interface card has then been used to analyse the influence of a thin flexible interlayer on laminate free-edge effects.

Plane strain elementary tensile test :

The test structure is an isotropic plate with an isotropic flexible behavior interlayer, ($m=1$), submitting to a tension displacement loading, Fig. 11.

Fig. 11: Elementary test

Fig. 12: Normal stiffness (MPa/mm)

A first interface law validation can be made by comparison between explicit stiffnesses obtained analytically by formula (7) to stiffnesses obtained numerically equal to the ratio between the interlayer stresses and the jump displacements, for different decreasing small thickness values. We note that for sufficiently thin thickness, the numerical normal stiffness converges towards the explicit one, Fig. 12. For this simple tensile test sample, it is not possible to obtain numerically the tangential stiffness by discretizing the interlayer, because the sliding and the shear stress vanish in this case.

To see if the interface law correctly restore the stresses and displacements at the interlayer, we have replaced the interlayer by a material surface where we have traduced the interface law using an interface card, elaborating by associating two finite elements in ABAQUS ; a spring finite element, and a contact finite element insuring the "non-interpenetrability" condition and authorising the weak sliding.

We can thus verify in figures 13 and 14, for example, that the interface card, whose results are referenced as "CI", restore the interlayer lateral displacement and the shear stress well that naturally tends to zero in this case.

Fig. 13: Interlayer lateral displacement

Fig. 14: Interlayer shear stress

Since the law and its implementation are validated, we have then used it to simulate the free-edge effects in a laminate, presenting a thin flexible interlayer.

Tensile test of a $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ laminate composite

Fig. 15: Interlaminar stresses at the free-edge Vicinity

Fig. 16: σ_{33} distribution along the free edge

For this study, we use the same geometrical and mechanical characteristics of the $(0^\circ,90^\circ)_s$ laminate used previously.

The first important test result undertaken in this part of the work shows that the stresses obtained by the interface card, with a certain degree of approximation representative of a flexible thin layer, are not singular, Fig. 15. These stresses have the same magnitude as the stresses obtained before using a transition evolutive behavior law.

Nevertheless, in Fig. 16, a loss of the free-edge stress gradient intensity can be seen. This can be explained by the flexible character of the interface, whose stiffnesses here correspond to those of pure resin. This is not the case for the evolutive behavior.

In conclusion, the established interface law is representative of a very thin flexible layer. It is defined on material surface and allows us to undertake numerical simulations of thin and flexible layer cheaply. Now, we are working on the global evolutive behavior tensor to establish a representative surface material interface law.

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